

Science technology & Digital finance

journal homepage: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf>**INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHODS FOR COMPUTER SCIENCE AND EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS****Khaydarov Bahrom¹, Tuychieva Nodira²**¹ Senior lecturer of Jizzakh branch of the University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, Uzbekistan.² Assistant of Jizzakh branch of the University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, Uzbekistan.
email: nodira070495@gmail.com**ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНФОРМАТИКЕ И ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ РОБОТОТЕХНИКЕ****Хайдаров Бахром¹, Туйчиева Нодира²**¹ Старший преподаватель Джизакского филиала Узбекского университета имени Мирзо Улугбека, Узбекистан.² Ассистент Джизакского филиала Узбекского университета имени Мирзо Улугбека, Узбекистан.электронная почта: nodira070495@gmail.com**INFORMATIKA VA TA'LIM ROBOTOTEXNIKA UCHUN INNOVATSION O'QITISH USULLARI****Xaydarov Bahrom¹, Tuychieva Nodira²**¹ Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston universiteti Jizzax filiali katta o'qituvchisi, O'zbekiston.² Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston universiteti Jizzax filiali assistenti, O'zbekiston.
elektron pochta: nodira070495@gmail.com**abstract**

Interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and attention and interest in the use of digital technologies in the educational process every day becomes stronger. This article is modern to enrich the imagination when studying computer science electronic textbooks, animation and video using pedagogical technologies highlights the importance of using tools today.

аннотация

Интерактивные методы, инновационные технологии, педагогическое внимание и интерес к использованию цифровых технологий в образовательном процессе с каждым днем становятся все сильнее. Эта современная статья, призванная обогатить воображение при изучении электронных учебников по информатике, анимации и видео с использованием педагогических технологий,

подчеркивает важность использования инструментов сегодня.

annotatsiya

Interfaol usullar, innovatsion texnologiyalar, pedagogik va o'quv jarayonida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishga e'tibor va qiziqish kundan-kunga kuchayib bormoqda. Ushbu maqola informatika elektron darsliklarini, pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda animatsiya va videofilmlarni o'rganishda tasavvurni boyitish uchun zamonaviy bo'lib, bugungi kunda vositalardan foydalanish muhimligini ta'kidlaydi.

Keywords:

Interactive learning, interactive method, multimedia, audio, slide, cases, technology.

Ключевые слова:

Интерактивное обучение, интерактивный метод, мультимедиа, аудио, слайды, кейсы, технологии.

Kalit so'zlar:

Interfaol ta'lim, interfaol usul, multimedia, audio, Slayd, ish, texnologiya.

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Introduction

In the rapidly developing world, educational institutions in the continuous education system, including higher new tasks for the teachers of educational institutions, that is, the taught subject there is a task to improve the quality of mastering. In this regard, also in the teaching of computer science different methods are used. One of them is modern information technology is to use. Interactive methods in teaching computer science in the next decade use carried out in several main directions. To these, knowledge with the help of a computer assessment, development and development of different types of educational programs, related to knowledge development of computer games and others.

The convenience of computer interactive methods in teaching computer science in some educational situations is modeling. The purpose of using modeling programs is teaching it was difficult to imagine when using other methods is to ensure that the materials are understandable. Using modeling present information to students in the form of computer multimedia in graphic mode be done. Therefore, they are significant in the in-depth study and learning process of informatics tend to show independence.

Research methodology

To get an answer to the question of what and how to teach in informatics, first of all, this at the current stage of the development of the science, it is necessary to clearly define the tasks of teaching informatics.

These tasks are common to all general sciences. However, it is continuous This is based on the concept of teaching informatics in the educational system and state educational standards it is necessary to analyze the specific aspects of the tasks in the teaching of informatics.

In determining the content of computer science education, informatics is a science and education on the other hand it is necessary to proceed from the imagination that it is a subject. Computer science and education the subject differs from each other primarily in the size and depth of its content.

The issue of the size of the educational material included in the computer science subject after the decision, in what sequence should this educational material be delivered to the students it is necessary to determine whether it is appropriate to give. Methodology of teaching computer science one of its features is to introduce students to the content of informatics and its specific scientific research determining the methods and ways of obtaining practical knowledge and skills must these include learning methods and modern pedagogy forms of organizing educational activities based on psychological research.

Methodological, programmatic, organizational and technical training for teaching the subject "Informatics" engaged in research and development of supplies, pedagogy and informatics can be considered as a branch of science.

Results

To solve the problem of planning the activities of the young generation in our republic to be able to find the necessary information, a mathematical model of an example or problem being solved to have skills such as being able to build and effectively use new technologies necessary conditions are being created. The form and style of teaching should be aimed at developing the thinking and creative abilities of young students. of the problem the difficult part is that, on the one hand, the student's thinking and creative ability development, on the other hand, about the world of modern computers is to give knowledge in an interesting and harmonious way. It is known that general secondary education demonstration is important in the teaching of informatics and natural sciences in schools [4 p. 340]. Especially, in chemistry, it is more dangerous to actually carry out an explosion (as a result of a reaction). However, it is safe and convenient to show it through multimedia. Also, other showing chemical processes and the process of solving many physical problems giving, expands students' imagination.

If computer science is taught with the help of digital technologies, the following will be achieved:

- ✓ Using the possibilities of the electronic study guide, teach the students the topic in full the possibility of explanation increases;
- ✓ their knowledge, skills and qualifications increase;
- ✓ moving images and animations play an important role in expanding students' imaginations plays;
- ✓ to practical work, i.e. solving examples and problems, giving real examples, more time is allocated for question-and-answer among students;
- ✓ students' ability to think creatively is formed;

✓ students get a positive lesson from the lesson, their interest in the lesson increases;

✓ development of students' imagination, logical thinking, informatics terms and provides opportunities to learn practical methods of programming.

Conclusion

The use of modern and information technologies in the educational system of our children formation and development of independent thinking, knowledge acquisition skills, educational field is one of the urgent tasks facing the representatives. Among all educational subjects modern didactic games in thorough and effective mastering based on computer science it has a big place. It reflects students' understanding of the given topics [5 p. 156]. It is carried out with the help of teaching methods in the assimilation of concepts and information. In order for all this to be at the level of demand, it is also in informatics education today the use of modern didactic-game technologies has a good effect.

The goal is to find ways to interest our youth in learning. Young people are new seeks technology. Our task is to provide them with innovative technologies to provide Teachers pay attention to these issues of computer science by promoting new didactic games and new innovative teaching methods and methods in teaching consists of The created multimedia electronic complex, visual methods are also here can be an example of this.

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